

THE ROLE OF STUDENT-STUDENT INTERACTION IN EFL CLASSROOMS

Mahbuba Rasulova

Tashkent State University of Law
Foreign Languages Department

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6021795>

The importance of peer interaction

Peer interactions are not merely a luxury to be enjoyed during lunch and after school. For maximum achievement, socialization, and healthy growth, constructive student-student connections are almost certainly a must. The following are some of the ways that positive student-student relationships help students achieve their educational goals (1980, Johnson)

Educational aspirations and accomplishment are influenced by peer interactions. Peers have a significant impact on students' educational goals and accomplishments. Interaction with academically driven classmates can dramatically boost accomplishment, especially when students are young and have low study abilities. The ability to use abilities in success settings is linked to being a member of welcoming and helpful peer connections.

(2) Peer interactions aid in the socialization of values, attitudes, and perspectives on life. Peer connections have been shown to play an important role in a child's socialization, giving expectations, models, and reinforcements that influence a wide range of social actions, attitudes, and viewpoints.

Contacts with peers are more frequent, intense, and varied than interactions with teachers. Children and adolescents learn attitudes, beliefs, and facts from their peers that adults cannot provide, such as the nature of gender relations and how they should be developed and controlled among peers. Students imitate one another's actions and identify with friends who have admired abilities in their interactions with peers. The nature of clothing and hair styles, the music that is appreciated, what is defined as fun and what is defined as distasteful, and what competences need to be exercised and developed are all dependent on identification with and imitation of peers. The same can be said about honing and polishing social positions. Children and adolescents can practice social roles in their connections with peers, which allows for a gradual expansion of communicative, aggressive, defensive, and cooperative abilities.

3) Peer interactions serve as indicators of future psychological well-being. The ability to establish interdependent, cooperative relationships is frequently cited as a sign of psychological well-being. Poor peer interactions in elementary school predict

psychological disturbance in high school, and poor peer ties in both elementary and high school predict adult psychological pathology, which comes as no surprise. Isolation from classmates is linked to anxiety, low self-esteem, poor interpersonal skills, emotional disabilities, and psychological disease.

(4) Students develop the social essential skills to reduce social isolation through peer relationships. Lack of social skills is linked to social isolation. Children's social abilities can be improved by constructive interaction with peers, reducing potential social isolation. Because peer acceptance is linked to a propensity to engage in social interaction, creating helpful and accepting interactions among students has the potential to influence both the amount of peer engagement and the development of social skills.

(5) Peer interactions have an impact on whether or not possible problem behaviors in adolescence, such as drug use, develop. Whether or not adolescents use illegal substances, drink too much alcohol, or engage in other problem or transition behaviors like sexual intercourse is strongly linked to their beliefs of their peers partaking in and approving of these behaviors. If a teenager's friends disapprove of such acts, the adolescent will be less likely to indulge in them.

(6) Children learn to control aggressive urges in the context of peer relationships. Children's mastery of aggressive impulses is linked to peer interaction involving activities like rough-and-tumble play.

(7) Peer interactions play a role in the formation of gender identity. Gender typing

is expanded, refined, and confirmed within the peer group. Gender appropriate attitudes are learnt and assimilated within the peer group.

(8) Peer interactions contribute to the creation of perspective-taking skills. Children and teenagers develop the ability to see situations and challenges from other viewpoints through interaction with peers.

(9) Attitudes about school are influenced by peer relationships. Peer rejection is linked to disruptive behavior in the classroom, hostile behavior, and an adverse effect in the classroom, as well as negative attitudes about other students and the school. Simply putting students in close proximity and allowing them to interact does not guarantee the above favorable consequences. It's crucial to consider the nature and quality of the interaction. Peer interactions must create feelings of belonging, acceptance, support, and compassion, rather than feelings of hostility and rejection, in order to be positive effects. Teachers must first ensure that students engage with one another, and then ensure that the interaction takes place in a supportive and accepting environment in order to develop constructive peer influences. To put it another way, teachers must be in charge of the major aspects that influence student-student interaction, such as how learning goals are constructed and how disagreements between ideas are handled. These two educational styles appear to have the best chance of fostering positive student-student interaction.

The examples of peer teaching

- A music teacher asks a student who has taken private trombone lessons to give

a special trombone lesson to their classmates.

- A college senior collaborates with a faculty member to teach a first-year college freshman year experience course.
- High school students who have taken a summer coding are assisting their peers in learning to code in groups.
- A clinical skills laboratory for other medical students is led by a fourth-year medical student.

The advantages of peer learning

1. It can improve students' attitudes toward learning

One of the advantages of peer teaching is that it can improve students' attitudes toward what they are studying and the learning process as a whole. For some students who are not interested in, being taught by a peer can break down the barriers. In peer groups, more students feel more at ease and inclined to seek assistance. Students may also feel more motivated since they are being taught by someone who has successfully learned and is enthusiastic about the content. To put it another way. They have a success story in front of them to motivate to accomplish similar outcomes.

2. It engages students through cooperative learning.

Individualized and competitive learning are two types of learning frameworks that are distinct from cooperative learning. In cooperative learning, students work together to deepen their understanding of a subject by offering what they can. Cooperative learning usually entails groups of students with varying levels of aptitude working together.

A collaborative classroom atmosphere naturally lends itself to a peer-to-peer learning dynamic. Because cooperative learning is essentially student-centered, it stands to reason that one of the most effective ways to create an engaging and cooperative learning experience is in a classroom led by students. Because it helps each student to have more ownership over their education, this learning structure actively engages students in the learning process.

3. It can help peer teachers gain confidence and sharpen their skills

It is also worth noting that peer teaching is not a one-way exchange. Peer teachers can benefit from participating in the peer learning process as well. You may observed how teaching a concept or ability to a friend helps you brush up on material or hone your skills if you have ever done so. Teaching anything is an effective approach to improve your own grasp of the material, according to large body of research. Peer leaders can gain a deeper grasp of the content as they plan classes, answer questions, demonstrate, and more.

Conclusion

The article sought to investigate the role and the importance of peer learning in EFL classrooms. Several empirical investigations revealed that peer learning had an important impact on students' language learning as they tended to learn the target language well when they were engaged in tasks and activities with their peers. Through the interview analysis in some research, students said that they found interesting to learn something with their friends and classmates in the classes

because they could have a chance to share their ideas and opinions, to speak in the target language more without any fear and shame, to learn new things from their peers.

Thoroughly examining the data from empirical studies, it should be highlighted

that teachers should optimize peer learning and peer interaction method during the classes. It is highly likely that this method would bring about more productive and fruitful learning outcomes.

References

1. Berlyne, D. Notes on intrinsic motivation and intrinsic reward in relation to instruction. In J. Bruner (Ed.), *Learning about learning* (Cooperative Research Monograph No. 15). Washington, D.C.: U.S. Department of Health, Education, and Welfare, Office of Education, 1966.
2. Deutsch, M. Cooperation and trust: Some theoretical notes. In M. Jones Ed.), *Nebraska symposium on motivation*. Lincoln, Neb.: University of Nebraska Press, 1962.
3. Glass, G. V Integrating findings: The meta-analysis of research. In L.
4. Shulman (Ed.), *Review of research in education* (Vol. 5). Itasca, Ill. Peacock, 1977.
5. Johnson, D. W. *The social psychology of education*. New York: Holt, Rinehart, & Winston, 1970.
6. Johnson, D. W. *Educational psychology*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice-Hall, 1979.
7. Johnson, D. W. Group processes: Influences on student-student interaction and school outcomes. In J. McMillan (Ed.), *Social psychology of school learning*. New York: Academic Press, 1980.
8. Johnson, D. W., & Johnson, R. *Learning together and alone: Cooperation, competition and individualization*. Englewood Cliffs, N.J.: Prentice Hall, 1975.
9. Ishnazarovna, M. N. (2021). Functional Varieties of Legal English in Writing Speech. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(2), 350-355.
10. Mahbuba Rasulova Ravshan qizi. (2021). EXAMINING APPLICABLE METHODS AND TECHNIQUES TO FOSTER EFL LEARNERS' SPEAKING SKILLS. *Eurasian Journal of Academic Research*, 1(9), 549-563. <https://in-academy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/227>
11. Qizi, Y. S. T. (2020). Religious speech and phonetic interference. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 10(6), 679-683.